

Original Research

An In Vitro Study to Evaluate Bond Strength by Surface Modification of Various Denture Teeth with Different Denture Base Materials

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Debonding of denture teeth from denture base materials is a common clinical complication affecting prosthesis longevity. Surface modification techniques may enhance bond strength. **Methods:** A total of 140 samples were prepared using two denture teeth types (Acry Plus and Acry Lux) and two denture base materials (Lucitone 199 and Lucitone FRS). Four surface treatments were applied: no modification, diatorics, metal pin attachment, and dichloromethane application. Bond strength was evaluated using a universal testing machine. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA, Tukey's post-hoc test, and unpaired t-test with significance at $p < 0.05$. **Results:** For heat-cured resin (Lucitone 199), dichloromethane and metal pin groups showed significantly higher bond strength ($p < 0.001$). For thermoplastic resin (Lucitone FRS), metal pin and diatorics demonstrated superior performance, while dichloromethane showed the lowest values. Heat-cured resin exhibited significantly higher bond strength compared to thermoplastic resin. **Conclusion:** Surface modification significantly influences bond strength. Chemical treatment is effective for heat-cured bases, whereas mechanical retention methods are preferable for thermoplastic bases.

Keywords: Bond strength, denture base resin, thermoplastic resin, dichloromethane, metal pin, diatorics

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INTRODUCTION

The organs of the human body operate through complex, interdependent mechanisms to maintain homeostasis and support daily physiological processes. Elderly individuals often present with comorbid conditions and age-related metabolic changes, rendering them more susceptible to oral health issues.^{1,2} Early dentures were fabricated from materials such as wood, ivory, bone, Bakelite, vulcanite, aluminium, celluloid, acrylic resin, and nylon.³ Nanoparticles are increasingly used in dentistry for various applications, including enhancing the mechanical properties of denture base resins.^{4,5} Recently 3D printing with help of intraoral scanner is also under research for complete denture formation. During the usage of a complete denture, patients come across various problems like fracture of the denture,

debonding of the tooth from the denture base, infection, loosening of the denture, loss of vertical dimension, etc.⁶ Improving masticatory efficiency by prosthodontic rehabilitation can aid in normalizing the nutritional status in certain partially edentulous non-obese and obese individuals.

To overcome these limitations, thermoplastic materials such as polyamides (nylon), acetal resins, epoxy resins, polystyrene, polycarbonate resins, polyurethane, and thermoplastic acrylic resins were introduced in dentistry as alternatives to conventional PMMA.⁷ The main advantage of thermoplastic resins lies in their monomer-free composition, making them biocompatible, non-toxic, and non-allergenic.⁸⁻¹²

Thermoplastic denture base materials exhibit superior aesthetics, enhanced fracture resistance, and increased

patient comfort.^{13,14} Their smooth, non-porous surface reduces bacterial adherence and tissue irritation.¹⁵

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This is an In vitro experimental study conducted in the Department of Prosthodontics and Crown & Bridge after obtaining Ethical Approval from Institutional Ethical Review Board.

Two denture base materials—Lucitone 199 (heat-cured PMMA) and Lucitone FRS (thermoplastic resin)—and two denture teeth types—Acry-Plus (acrylic) and Acry-Lux (cross-linked resin)—were used. Each combination underwent four ridge-lap surface treatments: no modification, diatorics, metal pin attachment and dichloromethane solvent application, with ten specimens per subgroup. (Figure – 1 & 2)

➤ **LUCITONE 199** [Heat cure denture base material]

Figure – 1 Lucitone199 Heat cure denture base material

➤ **LUCITONE FRS** [Thermoplastic denture base material]

Figure – 2 Lucitone FRS Thermoplastic denture base material

Figure – 3 Total sample size (N = 140 samples)

Wax blocks were fabricated following the Japanese Industrial Standard (JIS T6506:1989). The Duplication mould & verification mould were prepared with the help of lab silicone, and samples were duplicated from them. (N = 140) (Figure – 3) The tooth was set at a 45-degree angle (Chai et al., 2000; Takahashi et al., 2000; Bragaglia et al., 2009) using protractor. (Figure - 4)

Figure – 4 Tooth was set at 45-degree angle using a protractor

These denture teeth were attached with two different types of denture base material, with four modifications on the ridge lap surface of the teeth.

1. No modification: No modification on the ridge lap area of the tooth.
2. 'T' shaped Diatorics: Making Diatorics on the ridge lap area of teeth with twist drills. (Figure – 5.1)
3. Metal pin attachment with cyanoacrylate adhesive: A Metal pin was attached to the ridge lap surface of the teeth with cyanoacrylate adhesive. (Figure – 5.2)
4. Applying chemical solvent: applying chemical solvent (DICHLOROMETHANE LIQUID) on the ridge lap surface of teeth. (Figure – 5.3)

Samples were acrylised by heat-cured - compression moulding technique and thermo-plasticised - injection moulding technique. For the compression moulding procedure, eighty prepared samples were flaked and subjected to dewaxing at 100 °C for five minutes. The samples were then compression moulded using a trial packing technique and subsequently polymerised in a water bath maintained at 165 °F for nine hours, following the conventional curing cycle.

Figure – 5.1 'T' shaped diatorics on ridge lap surface

Figure – 5.2 Attachment of metal pin

Figure – 5.3 Applying chemical solvent on ridge lap surface

For the thermoplasticized injection moulding technique, the remaining sixty samples were flaked and dewaxed at 100 °C for five minutes. Each thermoplastic cartridge was then heated in an electrical cartridge furnace at a temperature of 550 °F to 560 °F for approximately fifteen minutes to achieve plasticization. The heated cartridge was aligned precisely with the opening of the flask, and the material was injected under consistent pressure. The injection pressure was maintained for three to five minutes, after which the flask was allowed to bench cool undisturbed for fifteen to twenty minutes before separation.

Specimens were tested using an Instron Universal Testing Machine at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min. (Figure – 6) Maximum load at failure (N) was recorded, and bond strength (MPa) was calculated by dividing the load by the bonded area. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS Software (IBM SPSS Statistical Software version 23). Statistical Tests - Mean, Standard Deviation (SD), one-way Analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Tukey's post-hoc tests, and Student's t-test (unpaired t-test) were performed for deriving conclusions. The level of significance (P-value) was set at 0.05.

Figure – 6 Sample testing with universal testing machine

RESULTS

When the teeth were bonded to the heat-cured Lucitone 199 base material, it was observed that the dichloromethane-treated group produced the highest bond strength values, followed closely by the metal-pin group. Table 1 demonstrates the pairwise comparison of mean bond strength among different surface treatment groups for Acry Plus teeth. The comparison between the no modification and diatoric groups showed no statistically significant difference (mean difference = -0.880; p = 0.993). In contrast, both metal pin (mean difference = -109.730; p < 0.001) and dichloromethane treatment (mean difference = -172.522; p < 0.001) exhibited significantly higher bond strength compared to the unmodified group. Similarly, diatoric preparation showed no significant difference with the unmodified group (p = 0.993), but demonstrated significantly

lower bond strength than both the metal pin (mean difference = -108.850; p < 0.001) and dichloromethane groups (mean difference = -171.642; p < 0.001). The metal pin group exhibited significantly higher bond strength than both unmodified (mean difference = 109.730; p < 0.001) and diatoric groups (mean difference = 108.850; p < 0.001). Furthermore, dichloromethane treatment demonstrated the highest bond strength, showing significant differences when compared with metal pin (mean difference = 62.792; p < 0.001), diatoric (mean difference = 171.642; p < 0.001), and unmodified groups (mean difference = 172.522; p < 0.001). Overall, dichloromethane treatment was the most effective method, followed by metal pin, while diatoric and unmodified groups showed comparable and lower bond strength values.

TABLE – 1 Lucitone 199 Denture Base with ACRY PLUS Teeth

Denture Base Material with Denture Teeth	Denture Base Material with Denture Teeth	Mean Difference in Bond Strength	P-value (Significance)	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
No modification	Diatorics	-0.880	0.993(N. SIG)	-9.647	7.887
	Metal Pin	-109.730	<0.001(SIG)	-118.497	-100.962
	Dichloromethane	-172.522	<0.001(SIG)	-181.289	-163.754
Diatorics	No modification	0.880	0.993(N. SIG)	-7.887	9.647
	Metal Pin	-108.850	<0.001(SIG)	-117.617	-100.082
	Dichloromethane	-171.642	<0.001(SIG)	-180.409	-162.874
Metal Pin	No modification	109.730	<0.001(SIG)	100.962	118.497
	Diatorics	108.850	<0.001(SIG)	100.082	117.617
	Dichloromethane	-62.792	<0.001(SIG)	-71.559	-54.024
Dichloromethane	No modification	172.522	<0.001(SIG)	163.754	181.289
	Diatorics	171.642	<0.001(SIG)	162.874	180.409
	Metal Pin	62.792	<0.001(SIG)	54.024	71.559

Table 2 demonstrates the pairwise comparison of mean bond strength among different surface treatment groups. All groups showed statistically significant differences (p < 0.001) except between metal pin and dichloromethane, which was not significant (p = 0.077). Both metal pin and dichloromethane groups exhibited significantly higher bond strength compared to the unmodified and diatoric groups. Additionally, the diatoric group showed significantly lower bond strength than the metal pin and dichloromethane groups but was higher than the unmodified group. Overall, dichloromethane and metal pin treatments demonstrated comparable performance and were the most effective, followed by diatoric, while the unmodified group showed the lowest bond strength.

Table – 2 Lucitone 199 Denture Base with Acrylux Teeth

Denture Base Material with Denture Teeth	Denture Base Material with Denture Teeth	Mean Difference in Bond Strength	P-value (Significance)	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
No modification	Diatorics	-12.422	<0.001 (SIG)	-19.371	-5.472
	Metal Pin	-116.000	<0.001(SIG)	-122.949	-109.050
	Dichloromethane	-122.448	<0.001(SIG)	-129.397	-115.498
Diatorics	No modification	12.422	<0.001(SIG)	5.472	19.371
	Metal Pin	-103.578	<0.001(SIG)	-110.527	-96.628
	Dichloromethane	-110.0260	<0.001(SIG)	-116.975	-103.076
Metal Pin	No modification	116.000	<0.001(SIG)	109.050	122.949
	Diatorics	103.578	<0.001(SIG)	96.628	110.527
	Dichloromethane	-6.448	0.077(N. SIG)	-13.397	0.501
Dichloromethane	No modification	122.448	<0.001(SIG)	115.498	129.397
	Diatorics	110.026	<0.001(SIG)	103.076	116.975
	Metal Pin	6.448	0.077(N. SIG)	0.5017	13.397

Table – 3 Lucitone FRS Denture Base with ACRY PLUS Teeth

Denture Base Material with Denture Teeth	Denture Base Material with Denture Teeth	Mean Difference in Bond Strength	P-value (Significance)	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
DIATORICS	Metal Pin	-38.010	<0.001(SIG)	-43.212	-32.807
	Dichloromethane	6.146	0.18(SIG)	0.9437	11.348
Metal Pin	DIATORICS	38.010	<0.001(SIG)	32.807	43.212
	Dichloromethane	44.156	<0.001(SIG)	38.953	49.358
Dichloromethane	DIATORICS	-6.146	0.18(SIG)	-11.348	-0.9437
	Metal Pin	-44.156	<0.001(SIG)	-49.358	-38.953

Table 3 presents the pairwise comparison of mean bond strength among the groups. A statistically significant difference was observed between diatorics and metal pin (mean difference = -38.010; p < 0.001), while the difference between diatorics and dichloromethane was not significant (mean difference

= 6.146; p = 0.18). The metal pin group showed significantly higher bond strength compared to both diatorics (mean difference = 38.010; p < 0.001) and dichloromethane (mean difference = 44.156; p < 0.001). Similarly, dichloromethane demonstrated significantly lower bond strength than metal pin

(mean difference = -44.156; $p < 0.001$) but showed no significant difference when compared with diatorics ($p = 0.18$). Overall, the metal pin group exhibited the highest bond strength, while diatorics and dichloromethane showed comparable performance.

Table 4 presents the descriptive statistics of bond strength for different surface modification groups. The

metal pin group exhibited the highest mean bond strength (147.84 ± 6.367), followed by the diatoric group (113.70 ± 3.212), while the dichloromethane group showed the lowest mean value (101.67 ± 5.439). The 95% confidence intervals and range values further support this trend, indicating superior performance of the metal pin group compared to the other surface modification methods.

Table – 4 Lucitone FRS Denture Base with ACRY LUX Teeth

SURFACE MODIFICATION	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	95% Confidence Interval		Minimum	Maximum
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
				DIATORICS	10		
Metal Pin	10	147.840	6.367	143.284	152.395	139.54	157.19
Dichloromethane	10	101.670	5.439	97.778	105.561	94.01	109.08

DISCUSSION

The success of complete and removable partial dentures depends on retention, support, stability, and patient satisfaction parameters such as chewing efficiency and aesthetics.¹⁶ Bond failure between denture teeth and denture base material remains a major cause of prosthesis failure.¹⁷

In the present study, dichloromethane and metal-pin modifications significantly improved bonding between acrylic teeth and heat-cured PMMA base. The solvent action of dichloromethane results in surface swelling, creating micropores and channels that enhance monomer penetration from the denture base into the denture teeth. This penetration promotes interdiffusion of polymers across the interface, forming a stronger, interwoven polymer network that improves cohesive strength and bond integrity.¹⁸ Additionally, surface topography altered by dichloromethane provides some micromechanical retention, further contributing to bond strength. Metal-pin modifications provide enhanced mechanical interlocking between the denture teeth and the base material, which complements the chemical bonding effects.¹⁹ Both treatments produced bond strengths exceeding the 110 N threshold recommended by JIS standards.²⁰

For thermoplastic resin, mechanical methods—diatorics and metal pins—yielded superior results compared to chemical treatment. Due to the high crystallinity and chemical resistance of thermoplastic resins, effective bonding relies on mechanical retention rather than chemical adhesion. Clinically, the results suggest that dichloromethane or metal-pin modification should be preferred with heat-cured

bases, whereas diatorics or metal-pin retention is more effective for thermoplastic materials. Manufacturers could consider prefabricated teeth with integrated metal pins to reduce debonding.^{21,22}

CONCLUSION

Surface modification significantly affects the bond strength between denture teeth and base materials. Dichloromethane and metal-pin modifications yielded the highest bond strength for heat-cured PMMA bases. For thermoplastic bases, metal-pin and diatoric modifications achieved satisfactory results, while chemical treatment was least effective.

Prefabricated acrylic teeth with integrated mechanical retention features could reduce debonding in clinical use.

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